

THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REAL SECTOR OF THE ECONOMY AND THE TRANSITION TO A "GREEN ECONOMY"

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the relationship between ecology and economics, the impact of the country's economic activity on the environment, as well as its results. The advantages of the transition to a "green economy" will be highlighted to significantly reduce the environmental risks associated with the country's economy and its production. In addition, this article also analyzes and explores the annual reports of the World Bank on the transition to a "green economy".

Keywords: *sustainable development, environment, environmental sustainability, environmental problems, "green economy", renewable energy sources, "green" transition, "green" jobs*

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматривается взаимосвязь между экологией и экономикой, влияние экономической деятельности страны на окружающую среду, а также ее результаты. Будут освещены преимущества перехода к "зеленой экономике", позволяющие значительно снизить экологические риски, связанные с экономикой страны и ее производством. Кроме того, в этой статье также анализируются и исследуются ежегодные отчеты Всемирного банка о переходе к "зеленой экономике".

Ключевые слова: *устойчивое развитие, окружающая среда, экологическая устойчивость, экологические проблемы, "зеленая экономика", возобновляемые источники энергии, "зеленый" переход, "зеленые" рабочие места.*

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada ekologiya va iqtisodiyot o'rtasidagi munosabatlar, mamlakat iqtisodiy faoliyatining atrof-muhitga ta'siri va uning natijalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tishning afzalliklari ta'kidlanadi, bu mamlakat iqtisodiyoti va uni ishlab chiqarish bilan bog'liq ekologik xavflarni sezilarli darajada kamaytiradi. Bundan tashqari, ushbu maqola Jahon bankining yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tish bo'yicha yillik hisobotlarini ham tahlil qiladi va o'rganadi.

Kalit so'zlar: barqarorlik, atrof-muhit, ekologik barqarorlik, ekologik muammolar, yashil iqtisodiyot, qayta tiklanadigan energiya, yashil o'tish, yashil ish o'rinlari

INTRODUCTION

The economic reforms carried out in recent years have created favorable conditions for Uzbekistan's transition to the next stage of market reforms. Economic reforms are more "green", and this process may be more beneficial for Uzbekistan if the economy is stable [1].

In fact, according to UNEP (the United Nations Environment Programming), the "Green economy" is an economy that contributes to "improving human well-being and social justice, as well as significantly reducing environmental risks and environmental scarcity." After all, the green economy is a new stage of development aimed at creating environmentally friendly products based on clean or "green" technologies that include new technologies, ecosystems that help and benefit nature. In addition, this system will undoubtedly directly open the way for new sectors of the economy that will help improve the nature of the country.

Due to the fact that the "green" transition for the economy of our country is a new stage, research on this issue has not yet been conducted. However, the World Bank is still conducting a number of studies and discussions. Below are a number of opinions based on these discussions regarding the measures taken towards a green economy, which are at the heart of the strategy for the transition to a green economy.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Uzbekistan is taking a step towards a "green" transition, because a "green" transition is not an independent process, but an integral part of the transition to a sustainable and inclusive market economy. Abroad, the "green growth" economic policy implementing this transition has been adopted by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) as a strategic direction for the long-term (until 2030) development of all Azo [2]. A step towards a "green" economy can be complemented by the introduction of innovative fiscal instruments. Economic modeling of the carbon and fuel tax can help the government better identify incentives for wider adoption of clean energy and clean fuels. According to a study by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, if existing production methods and consumption levels are maintained, the flora and fauna of the world will grow from 61 to 72 percent in 2050 compared to 2000, which, in turn, may lead to the irreversible disappearance of 7.5 million square meters of natural areas. Rational and efficient use of the world's natural resources instead of information can save US\$ 2 trillion per year for the next generation by 2050 [3]. The sad thing is that in developed countries, from 1 kg to 3 kg of solid household waste per capita is generated daily. In the US, this figure increases by 10 percent every 10 years. And in Russia, the area of landfills is 2000 square meters. In the UK, in fact, over the past 5 years, 7 million tons of waste have been recycled and reused within the framework of special programs. This is 6 million. greenhouse gas emissions into the atmosphere, 10 million tons of primary materials and 10 million liters of water savings. There are 8 thousand 700 in this area a workplace has been created. This, in turn, proved how useful the green economy is for the country's economy and the creation of new jobs [4].

According to a study conducted by the World Bank, the directions of the formation of a "green economy" :

- Development of renewable energy sources;
- Improvement of the waste management system;
- Improvement of the water resources management system;

Development of "clean", sustainable "green" transport;
Development of organic farming in agriculture;
Improving energy efficiency in housing and communal services;
Improving the efficiency of ecosystem conservation and management;
Creation of "green technologies" and development of sales markets.

Uzbekistan's transition from a planned economy to a market economy in 2016 began. Market reforms have intensified in many important industries. The government managed to implement reforms during the COVID pandemic, while reducing poverty, supporting economic growth and stabilizing the economy. These efforts have yielded the intended results, and today people in Uzbekistan feel an improvement in well-being and living conditions. At the next stage of economic reforms, the goal is to halve poverty and turn Uzbekistan into a country with above-average incomes (UMIC) by 2030. By implementing "green" goals in economic reforms, Uzbekistan will be able to strengthen the transition process and increase profits from this process. This synergy is also recognized in the "strategy of transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a green economy".

So why should Uzbekistan switch to a "green economy"? This is caused by a number of factors, including:

- ✓ Most of the energy consumed in the national economy is produced using non-renewable natural resources.;
- ✓ Limited supply of these resources;
- ✓ Environmental pollution as a result of rapid industrial development;
- ✓ Lack of water;
- ✓ Environmental problems associated with the drying up of the Aral Sea are increasing.
- ✓ Uzbekistan for the last thirty years of independence and reforms

Thanks to environmental protection and forestry measures, significant progress has been made in combating the effects of climate change. Current national environmental plans, as well as goals, remain central elements of the transition to a

low-carbon and "green" economy. But there are still problems with the lack of irrigation and drinking water, reliable electricity supply, which include recent large-scale power outages, unprecedented sand and dust storms may be evidence. These problems, which negatively affect people, communities, the environment and infrastructure, are a reminder that much more needs to be done to ensure a "green" future of Uzbekistan [5].

The Government of Uzbekistan strives for a model of economic growth based on sustainable and efficient use of natural resources, low-carbon energy, pollution reduction and preparedness for the consequences of natural disasters and climate change. After all, sustainable development is a state of long-term balanced, continuous economic development based on full satisfaction of the needs of the population, and development that does not jeopardize the ability to meet the needs of future generations is sustainable economic development.

The objects of sustainable development according to the traditional approach are:

- ✓ Maximizing economic growth and fully satisfying the needs of the market system;
- ✓ Market failures can be corrected with the help of the macroeconomic policy of the state.
- ✓ According to the approach to sustainable development:
- ✓ Maximizing economic growth and meeting the needs of the population will ultimately lead to an increase in the well-being of the population.;
- ✓ Violation of nature leads to social relations in society, reduction of production and consumption, increase in poverty;
- ✓ Along with natural resources, economic progress is provided by information and cognitive resources.;
- ✓ Many types of natural resources are not valuable, but are a source of economic scarcity and decline.;
- ✓ Methods of measuring wealth accumulation do not take into account the depletion and degradation of natural resources;

✓ With the development of the economy, traditional natural resources are reduced.

International development partners "green" of Uzbekistan until 2030 helps in the implementation of the transition strategy [6] and the development of a long-term perspective of decarbonization of the economy by 2050.

Green economy ("green economy") the purpose of the concept is to ensure sustainable economic growth and increase investment activity, while improving the quality of environmental protection and social integration.

The agreed green growth priorities include:

- Disaster preparedness and resilience to climate change by protecting the population, providing financial and other emergency assistance to affected areas, population groups and economic sectors;
- Market reforms, inclusive policy in the field of agriculture and water management, sustainable and efficient use of natural resources through the involvement of the private sector in relevant processes;
- "Green" development of industry and economy by reducing emissions, modernizing enterprises, improving energy efficiency and reducing greenhouse gas emissions;
- "Green" investments and innovations to support the "green" transition of economic sectors;
- Support to the population and territories most affected by sustainable and inclusive urbanization and the transition to a green economy, including the development of competencies and the creation of green jobs.

The Waste Management Strategy for 2019-2028 is aimed at optimizing the collection of urban waste and improving management in the transition to a regional approach. Waste management should be addressed comprehensively, taking into account the sustainability of operations, financing, legislation, monitoring and enforcement, environmental management and social integration aimed at achieving long-term sustainability for the entire population.

It is gratifying that “Hamkorbank”, one of the first private banks in Uzbekistan, cooperates with the Dutch development Bank on "green" loans in order to finance environmentally friendly technologies and equipment that reduce environmental emissions and energy consumption, as well as the introduction of energy-saving heating and cooling systems. This direction is a novelty both for domestic entrepreneurs and for the Partner Bank itself.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Today, Uzbekistan understands the unique opportunity to overcome the growth thresholds according to its current development model and strengthen its economic competitiveness in the global market, which is becoming more and more aware of the climate and ecology. Building on the acceleration of structural reforms, the country is taking steps for its economy, people and the planet to chart the path to a "green" model of low-carbon growth and climate resilience based on flexible, inclusive, sustainable and efficient use of natural resources (mibs) while creating new jobs in developing sectors. But in order to become a more sustainable and "green" economy, the country needs to work on existing environmental problems and other risk factors that slow down economic growth.

✓ In order to strengthen the role of the "green economy" in ensuring sustainable development in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to develop the following measures:

✓ First, priority should be given to projects aimed at informing the public about the causes of environmental degradation.

✓ Secondly, it is necessary to improve the quality of public administration in the field of environmental protection.

✓ Thirdly, it will be advisable to encourage the use of "green" technologies in the production and production of environmentally friendly products through the implementation of a policy of "green" public procurement.

✓ Fourth, it is necessary to effectively use "green" technologies to increase the energy potential of the national economy.

✓ Finally, fifthly, in the process of modernization of the economy, it is necessary to increase the volume of public investment in "green" infrastructure.

We have no doubt that by implementing the measures listed above, we will be able to ensure a more developed economy based on sustainable development for future generations.

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